

**ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF DRY SEASON FLUTED PUMPKIN
PRODUCTION AMONG SMALLHOLDER FARMERS IN SOUTHEAST,
NIGERIA**

¹Utobo O.

²Ezeano C.I.

²Nwankwo F.O.

²Onugu C.U.

³Nte I.N.

⁴Anaduaka C.C.

¹National Horticultural Research Institute, Mbato Outstation, Okigwe, Imo State, Nigeria

²Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka

³Ebonyi State University, Abakaliki

⁴University of Nigeria, Nsukka

Email: utobo1984@gmail.com +234 7031683225

Abstract. The study analyzed the economics of dry season fluted pumpkin production among smallholder farmers in Southeast, Nigeria using 400 respondents selected through multistage, purposive and proportionate sampling techniques. Data were collected using structured questionnaire administered in the form of interview schedule. Data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics, Cobb-Douglas production function, and gross margin. Results showed that 80% of fluted pumpkin farmers were females while 20% of them were males and aged 38years that operated on the average of 0.7ha, which earned them average annual income of N 98,000.00 from fluted pumpkin. Results further revealed that the farmers had formal education with 12.20years average farming experiences and average household size of 7

persons. Results of gross margin analysis showed that fluted pumpkin production is profitable with cost-return-ratio of 1:1.82 and the profit of N67,500. Regression results showed that 85% of the fluctuations in the output of fluted pumpkin in the dry season were accounted for by the variables included in the model such that farm size (0.623), farming experience (0.222), cost of manure (0.159), cost of irrigation water (0.323), capital input (0.093) and education level (0.423) were significant and positively related to output of fluted pumpkin. Contrarily, cost of agrochemical (-0.497) and age (-0.475) were negative and significantly related to output of fluted pumpkin. It would be concluded that fluted pumpkin production in Southeast Nigeria, was profitable. There is need for farmers and youths who are yet to engage in agriculture especially fluted pumpkin production to tenaciously embrace its cultivation due to its economic viability, profitability, productivity and sustainability in Southeast Nigeria.

Keywords: Dry Season, Economics, Fluted Pumpkin, Production, Smallholder

INTRODUCTION

Fluted pumpkin is a very important vegetable that is popular in West Africa. It belongs to the family *Telfaria occidentalis* Hook F. *cucurbitaceae* (Sakpere, Ajayi, and Adelusi, 2016). It is a leafy vegetable that produces fruits. Leafy vegetables are herbaceous plants used for culinary purposes (Schreinemachers, Simmons and Wopereis, 2018). They are used to increase the dietary quality of soups. The fruit on full maturity has a weight of 10kg and an appearance of 10 distinctive longitudinal ribs on the surface (Chukwudi and Agbo, 2014). It is popular in West Africa. The edible part of this vegetable are the large red seeds, leaves and young shoots used for traditional soup. Protein rich seed can be roasted or grounded for use in porridge. The flesh of the fruits has good oil content which can be used as cooking oil (Sakpere, Ajayi, and Adelusi, 2019).

Amongst the different vegetable foods, production and consumption of fluted pumpkin is very important because of its contribution to good health by providing

inexpensive sources of minerals and vitamins needed to supplement people's diet which are mainly carbohydrates (Akanni-John, Shaib-Rahim, Eniola, Elesho, 2020). Fluted pumpkin is the most important and extensively cultivated food and income generating crops in many parts of Africa (Adebisi-Adelani, Olajide-Taiwo, Adeoye, Olajide-Taiwo, 2011). Fluted pumpkin consumption has improved over the years and it is an important component of the daily diets of Nigerians (Abu and Asembler. 2011 and Ulger, Songurn, Grak, Cakiroglu. 2018). Due to its hypolipidemic action, it lowers blood cholesterol and thus protects from a large range of associated complications like cardiac problems, hypertension and diabetes (Margret, 2011 and Ulger, *et al.* 2018).

The ecological zones in the country support varieties of crop production, ranging from cereals in the savanna region, root and tree crops in the rain forest and vegetables in all ecological zones (Akpan, Udo, Basse, Inya-gha and Udo 2012). Vegetable production has been inconsistent in Nigeria; for instance, in 2005 about 4924.9 thousand tones were produced, while 2487.7 thousand tones were produced in 2006 (Ibeawuchi, Okoli, Alagba, Ofor, Emma-Okafor, Peter-Onoh, and Obiefuna, 2015). Fluted pumpkin leaves and seeds are good sources of protein, mineral salts, sugars, vitamins, and essential oils that increase man's resistance to disease (Sakpere, *et al.* 2019). (Layade, Adeoye, Ngbede and Utobo, 2020) asserted that increased fluted pumpkin production improved food security and offer employment opportunities to many rural women in Nigeria. In the Southern region of Nigeria, fluted pumpkin is popular due to its high consumption rate, easily traced to its affordability (Layade, *et al.* 2020). Waterleaf (*Talinum triangulae*) and fluted pumpkin (*Telfairia occidentalis*) are among the major leafy vegetables grown by farmers in the southeastern region of Nigeria (Akpan, Udoh, Basse, Inya-Agha, and Udoh, 2012). The popularity of these two major vegetable crops had been linked to low cost per unit of resource use in production, short gestation period and quick returns on investment compared to other vegetable crops (Akpan et al, 2012 and WHO 2020).

Production is the organized activity of transforming resources into finished products in the form of goods and services; the objective of production is to satisfy the demand for such transformed resources (Bond and Alex, 2021; jiang, 2020). In economic theory, a production function is described in terms of maximum output that can be produced from a specified set of inputs, given the existing technology available to the farm (Utobo, Ngbede and Nwankwo, 2018). In general, a production function is a specification of how the quantity of output behaves as a function of the inputs used in production (Utobo, Anyikwa, Ekpunobi and Nwankwo, 2021).

However, several studies in Nigeria have been carried out to analyze economics/profitability of crops and more specifically vegetables. Amongst these studies are:

Nwauwa and Omonona (2010) examined fluted pumpkin production under irrigation system in Ilorin using 100 respondents selected purposively with data collected using questionnaire. Data collected were analysed using descriptive and Cobb Douglas production function. Results showed that fertilizer and labour, plot size and labour as significant factors which contributed to technical and allocative efficiency respectively. Farmers on the field training are needed to improve efficiency of resource utilization is crucial for increased productivity.

Ayoola (2014) assessed the profitability of vegetable farming under irrigation and rain-fed systems using the gross margin, net profit, benefit-cost, shepherd-future and regression approach on data collected from 200 farmers selected through multistage sampling technique. Results showed that investment on irrigation for vegetable production would be worthwhile for growing commercial vegetable enterprise in the study area. Results further showed that vegetable production is profitable under existing production systems with an average net income of ₦65,800.90/ha on a mean farm size of 0.51ha. Cost of fertilizer and farm size were underutilized. Continuous training and re-training of farmers are necessary to improve their productivity in terms of efficiency of resource utilisation.

Nwosu, Onyeneke and Okoli, (2012) examined the constraints faced by fluted pumpkin farmers in Abor Mbaise Local Government Area of Imo State using 120 farmers selected through random sampling. Data collected were analysed using principal component method of factor analysis. Results showed that lack of credit facilities, lack of availability of inputs, pests and disease infestation, inadequate information about input and output prices, and poor road network constrained farmers in the study area. There is need for redesigning of agricultural policies and programme to reduce the constraints

None of the studies seem to have addressed the lapses of fluted pumpkin farmers in Nigeria. In Southeastern Nigeria, fluted pumpkin have formed virtually part of rural and urban households' diet and nutrition, food security, poverty alleviation, women empowerment and improved human nutrition through the provision of balanced diets. To this end, the production of fluted pumpkin might have not received the appropriate public and institutional support despite its significant contributions to households' nutrition and food security. It is against these backgrounds that the study set to analyze the economics/profitability of smallholder fluted pumpkin farmers in Southeast, Nigeria with the following research questions; What are the socioeconomic characteristics of smallholder fluted pumpkin farmers? What is the input and output relationship of smallholder fluted pumpkin production? Is fluted pumpkin production profitable? What are the constraints to fluted pumpkin production in the study area? A null hypothesis was tested to guide the study in arriving at meaningful results. **H₀₁**: The level of input utilization of smallholder fluted pumpkin farmers has no significant effect on output of fluted pumpkin.

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted in Southeast Nigeria. Southeast Nigeria (Igboland) is a region of Nigeria that borders Cross river state to the east, the River state to the south, Benue State in the north and on longitude 8° 30¹N and latitude 5° 45¹ N. It is composed of the following states: Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu, and Imo with population of 16.4 million people (National Population Commission, NPC, 2006) and

projected population of 22 million people (National Bureau of Statistics, NBS, 2017). Southeast Nigeria has a total land mass of approximately 41,440Km² square kilometers. Agriculture is the major backbone of the economy of southeastern Nigeria (Ebonyi State Agricultural Development Programme, EBADEP, 2016).

The population for the study comprised of all the smallholder fluted pumpkin farmers in Southeast, Nigeria. The sample of smallholder-fluted pumpkin farmers used for the study was selected from the five States that make up Southeast zone of Nigeria. Three states namely Ebonyi, Enugu and Imo were the sample frame where the sample size for the study was drawn.

From Ebonyi, Imo and Enugu that were purposively selected because of their dominance in fluted pumpkin production and in line with the list of Agricultural Development Programme (ADP) of the three states: Ebonyi has six thousand six hundred and fifty five (6,655) smallholder fluted pumpkin farmers, Enugu has four thousand five hundred and seventy-two (4,572) smallholder fluted pumpkin farmers, Imo has six thousand seven hundred and thirteen (6,713) smallholder fluted pumpkin farmers. The summation of these figures gave seventeen thousand nine hundred and forty (17,940) smallholder fluted pumpkin farmers which formed the sampling frame.

In view of the above, the Taro Yamane sample size determination formula was used to determine the sample size of the study from the sampling frame as stated above, thus:

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2} \quad (1)$$

Where:

N = Population of the Study

n = Sample Size

(e) = Level of significance

1 = Unit (a constant)

Note: (e) = 0.05

$$n = \frac{17940}{1 + 17840(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{17940}{44.85} = 400.00$$

Purposive, and multistage sampling techniques were used in the selection of the respondents for this study. The first stage involved the purposive selection of three states out of the five states in Southeast Nigeria: Ebonyi, Enugu, and Imo.

Stage II: two (2) senatorial zones were selected in each State to give six (6) Senatorial Zones.

Stage III: two (2) Local Government Areas were selected in each senatorial zone to give twelve (12) Local Government Areas.

Stage IV: three (3) communities were selected in each of the LGAs to give thirty-six 36 communities used for this study.

Recall the sample frame of the study and the sample size of four hundred (400) smallholder fluted pumpkin farmers, was proportionately distributed among the thirty-six (36) communities at 2.23% according to Umeh *et al.*, (2019).

The study used questionnaire that was administered in the form of interview schedule for data collection. Data collected for this study were analyzed using the following tools, namely: descriptive statistics, Cobb-Douglas functional form of stochastic frontier, Costs and returns analysis. Specifically, Objectives I was achieved using descriptive statistics such as tables, frequencies and percentages. Objective II was achieved using Cobb-Douglas functional form of stochastic frontier. Objective III was achieved using costs and returns analysis. However, the computer software used was SPSS.

Model Specification

The following models were used for the study; Cobb-Douglas stochastic frontier model, Gross margin analysis.

The implicit form of the Cobb-Douglas functional form of stochastic frontier is stated implicitly and explicitly as follows.

$$Y=f(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5, e) \quad (2)$$

Where,

Y= Value of output (Kg); X₁= Farm size (ha); X₂= Labour (mandays); X₃= Capital (Naira);

X₃=Cost of fluted pumpkin seeds (Naira); X₄=Cost of fertilizer (Naira); X₅=Cost of agro-chemicals (Naira)

The functional form was explicitly stated as:

$$\text{Log } Y = \text{Log } a_0 + a_1 \text{Log} x_1 + a_2 \text{Log} x_2 + a_3 \text{Log} x_3 + a_4 \text{Log} x_4 + a_5 \text{Log} x_5 + \text{et} \quad (3)$$

Where,

Log = Natural Logarithm; Y = Output; X₁ --- X₅ = Inputs;

a_i = *Coefficient of explanatory variables*; et = error term; a_0 = Regression constant

Testing of Hypotheses

The hypothesis for the study was tested using F-test at 5% level of significance.

Quantitatively,

$$F^*_{cal} = \frac{R^2/(K-1)}{(1-R^2)/(N-K)} \quad (4)$$

Where:

N = Number of Observations; K = Number of Variables; R² = Coefficient of Determination

Decision Rule;

If $F^*_{cal} > F^*_{tab}$, reject the null hypothesis, H₀;

If $F^*_{cal} < F^*_{tab}$, accept the null hypothesis, H₀.

Gross margin is the gross income from an enterprise less the variable costs incurred in achieving production. The formula for gross margin is stated thus;

$$GM = TR - TVC \quad (5)$$

Where; GM = Gross Margin, TR = Total Revenue, TVC = Total Variable Cost.

While the farmers' profit was calculated by gross margin less the total fixed cost.

$$II = GM - TFC \quad (6)$$

Where; Π = Profit, GM = gross margin, TFC = total fixed cost

However, return to investment is calculated as: $\frac{TR}{TC}$ (7)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data collected for this study were analyzed relative to the stated specific objectives of the study such that the specific objectives of the study formed the major sub-headings.

Table 1. The Socioeconomic Characteristics of Fluted Pumpkin Farmers

Variable	Freq (N=400)	Percentage (%)	Mean X
Sex			
Males	80	20.00	
Females	320	80.00	
Age			
< 30	140	35.00	
30-40	178	44.50	
41-50	62	15.50	38.10
>51	20	5.00	
Marital status			
Married	170	42.50	
Single	70	17.50	
Divorced	40	10.00	
Widow	120	30.00	
Level of education			
No formal education	50	12.50	
FSLC	96	24.00	
JSS/SSS	128	32.00	
OND/HND	116	29.00	
B.SC/M.SC/ Ph.D	10	2.50	
Farming experience			
<5	47	11.75	
5-10	139	34.75	
11-15	164	41.00	12.20
>15	50	12.50	
Farm size(ha)			
<1	330	82.50	
1-3	54	13.50	0.70
>3	16	4.00	
Annual Farm Income			
< 100,000	286	71.50	
100,000- 200,000	94	23.50	98,000
> 200,000	20	5.00	
Household size			
<5	120	30.00	
5-10	212	53.00	7.00

>10	68	17.00
Extension Contact		
Yes	116	29.00
No	284	71.00
Co-operative membership		
Yes	340	85.00
No	60	15.00

Source: Field Survey 2023

Table 1 revealed that 80% of fluted pumpkin smallholder farmers were females while 20% of them were males. This implied that females were more engaged in fluted pumpkin production compared to their male counterparts in the study area. This finding agreed with the findings of Addebisi and Adejumo (2017) and Jobirov, Yuejie, Kibona (2022) who reported that women were more involved in vegetable production.

The results also showed that the smallholder fluted pumpkin farmers had average age of 38years. This implied that the farmers were active and energetic and able to work on their farms in the absence of hired labour. This is consistent with the findings of Esiobu *et al.*, (2019) who reported that farmers in their active working age are adopters, innovative and good risk managers.

Results further revealed that majority (43%) of the farmers were married. This finding is in consonance with the findings of Eze *et al.*, (2015) who reported that married females were mostly engaged in farming activities with their household as a way of diversifying their agricultural engagement and improvement in the household income.

The result further showed that majority, 32% had basic education. This agreed with the findings of Gideon *et al.*, (2018) who reported that educated farmers knows the intricacies in farm business and input mix for effective farm operation especially crop production.

Results of farming experience showed that fluted pumpkin farmers in the study area had 12years average farming experiences. This implied that farmers' with more years of farming experiences would be more efficient in input combination, better

knowledge of climate change issues, market fluctuations in prices and as such would operate a more effective and profitable agricultural production activities. This was also in conformity with Esiobu *et al.*, (2019) who reported that past knowledge of agricultural production management gives the farmers the leverage of setting attainable objectives bearing in mind the cost implications of their decisions and its attendant risks as well as effectiveness in resource utilisation.

The results of the farm size of fluted pumpkin farmers revealed that they operated on the average of 0.7ha of land. This corroborated with the findings of Oladeebo and Oyetunde, (2018) and Onumadu *et al.*, (2019) who reported that Nigerian agricultural size of holdings were fragmented, hence the smallholder nature of the farmers.

Results also showed the average income of fluted pumpkin farmers to be ₦98,000.00. This implied that the farmers were still very poor. This is consistent with the findings of Nwibo and Okorie (2013) who reported that farmers with higher farm income would easily be involved in entrepreneurial activities than those of their counterpart who have poor farm income.

Results further showed that the farmers had average household size of 7 persons. This implied the household size of the farmers add labour to their farms. This agreed with the findings of Ovharhe *et al.* (2020) who stated that farmers engaged at the different agricultural subsectors had a household size range of 6–10 persons primarily to solve labour problems.

Results of extension contact indicated that majority, 71% of the farmers had no contact with extension agents. This agreed with the findings of Benjamin *et al.*, (2020) who reported that inadequate extension contacts are detrimental to the productivity of farmers due to poor advisory services and on farm teachings.

Table 2. Cobb Douglas Result of Input and Output Relationship of fluted Pumpkin in Dry Season

Variables	Double-log function		
	Coefficients	Std error	t-values
log age	-0.475**	0.127	-3.740
log farming experience	0.222***	0.026	8.657
log farm size	0.623**	0.139	4.469
log household size	0.179	0.151	1.187
log cost of manure	0.159**	0.065	2.439
log cost of seed	0.053	0.029	1.811
log cost of agrochemical	-0.497***	0.080	-6.215
log capital input	0.093**	0.133	2.851
log man days of labour	-0.064	0.090	-0.708
log of cost of irrigation water	0.323***	0.054	5.927
education level	0.423**	0.120	3.523
cooperative society	0.119**	0.040	3.162
extension visit	-0.059	0.149	-0.395
Constant +	7.267***	1.401	5.187
R ²	0.848		
R ² adjusted	0.816		
F-ratio	23.457***		

Source: Field Survey, 2023; ** and *= significant at 1% and 5%, respectively**

Results of Table 2 showed that the coefficient of multiple determination (R^2) was 0.848 which implied that 85% of the fluctuation in the output (regressand) of fluted pumpkin in the dry season in the study area were accounted for by the regressor variables included in the model. Similarly, the F-ratio value of 23.457 which was statistically significant at 1% probability level showed that the coefficients of the regressor variables included in the model was statistically different from zero, hence the goodness-of-fit of the Cobb Douglas model.

The farm size (0.623) was significant and positively related to output at 5% significant level. This implied that increase in the area under cultivation would lead to increase in output of fluted pumpkin. This corroborated with the findings of Busari *et al.*, (2017) who reported that increase in farm size leads to increased output.

Results of farming experience (0.222) were significant and positively related to the output of fluted pumpkin. This finding is in agreement with the findings of

Onubuogu (2013) who stated that the more years of farming experiences a farmer had, the more his/her capacity to optimal usage of inputs, proper understanding of climate change and marketing mix for higher productivity in their agricultural undertakings.

Results also showed that the cost of manure was 0.159, which was significant at 5% level. This implied that cost of manure was positively related to the quantity of fluted pumpkin produced. Organic manure improves soil fertility by accumulating a large amount of plant nutrients in the soil and preventing their losses through lixiviation (Büchi *et al.*, 2018). The use of organic manure is ideal for pumpkin production because they can supply adequate nutrients and suppress weed growth thereby reducing cost of production as a result of its usage.

Education level (0.423), the coefficient of educational level was positive and significantly related to output of fluted pumpkin. This showed that increase in the education level of a farmer would lead to increase in fluted pumpkin output. This finding was supported by the finding of Chukwu (2013) and Yaseen *et al.*, (2016) who reported that the educational attainment of a farmer is always the function of skills at his disposal, the capacities for effective use of input, and adopters of innovations as well as processing and packaging of products compared to those without formal education.

Capital input (0.093) the coefficient of capital was positive and significant. This implied that increase in the magnitude of capital input used in fluted pumpkin production leads to increased output of fluted pumpkin produced in the study area. This result was consistent with the findings of Onumadu *et al.*, (2014) who reported that improvement in the supply of farm capital would translate into higher yields of fluted pumpkin in virtually all the fluted pumpkin producing states of Southeast

Cost of agrochemical (-0.497) was negative and significantly related to output of fluted pumpkin in the study area. This is inconsonance with the findings of Adekunle *et al.*, (2020) who reported that high cost of agrochemical and its adverse

effect on soil leads to low productivity of vegetables and well as increased cost of vegetable production.

Cost of irrigation water (0.323) is significant and positively related to the output of fluted pumpkin. This implied that increased supply of water in the form of irrigation especially in the dry season would lead to increased output of leafy vegetables. This agreed with the finding of Anthony *et al.*, (2021) who reported that the cost of irrigation water for dry season vegetable production come with not cost and in areas where cost is attached, it is always very minimal.

Ho₁: The level of input utilization of smallholder fluted pumpkin farmers has no significant effect on output of fluted pumpkin. From the point of view the significant F-ratio of 23.457 that was significant at 1% significant level, the stated null hypothesis was rejected and the study would conclude that the level of input utilization of smallholder fluted pumpkin farmers had significant effect on output of fluted pumpkin in the dry season in Southeast, Nigeria.

Gross Margin Analysis of fluted pumpkin production per Hectare in Dry Season

The profitability of an enterprise is a function of efficiency of input combination at least cost and the going market prices of input and output. In view of this, the profitability of fluted pumpkin production was analyzed using gross margin analysis and results presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Gross Margin Analysis of fluted pumpkin production per Hectare in Dry Season

S/N	ITEMS	Total QTY	Unit Cost (₦)	TR & TC (₦)
A	Returns			
	Fluted Pumpkin (leaf output)	25bundles (30kg)	5500	137,500
	Fluted Pumpkin (pod output)	10 pods	1200	12,000
	Total Revenue (TR)			149,500
B	Variable Cost (VC)			
I	Labour cost			
	Site Clearing	12 man-days	700	8,400
	Making of heaps or beds	26 man-days	1000	26,000
	Sowing of seed	2 man-days	500	1,000

	Weeding (herbicides)	3 man-days	600	1,800
	Fertilizer application	2 man-days	500	1,000
	Total labour cost			37,200
II	Operating Input Costs			
	Cost of seeds	15kg	1000	15,000
	Fertilizer	10kg	500	5,000
	Cost of agro-chemicals	3litres	3000	9000
	Transportation	Lump sum		3,000
	Total Operating Input Cost			32,000
	Total Cost (TVC)			69,200
C	Fixed Costs (FC)			
	Depreciation excluding land (tools and equipment)			12,800
	Total fixed cost (TFC)			12,800
	Total Costs (TC) =TFC+TVC			82,000
	Gross Margin = TR-TVC			80,000
	Profitability (TR-TC)			67,500
	Cost-Return-Ratio (TR/TC)			1:1.82

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Results of Table 3 showed that the total return on the production of fluted pumpkin in the study area was ₦149, 500 and the gross margin of ₦80, 000. This implied that the profitability of fluted pumpkin production increased as the gross margin increases, therefore the gross margin of ₦80, 000 was the contribution of fluted pumpkin production to offsetting the fixed costs of the fluted pumpkin business. From Table 3, it was observed that fluted pumpkin production was profitable farm business and this further justified by the cost-return-ratio of 1:1.82, which indicated the profitability of fluted pumpkin production which therefore implied that every ₦1 invested would generate a profit of ₦1.82k which is equivalent to 182% return on investment. This agreed with economic theory where it postulated that an enterprise would be considered viable when the cost-return-ratio of such enterprise is equal to or greater than one and was supported by the findings of Olowa and Olowa (2016) and Osuji *et al.*, (2022) who reported high return on investment in fluted pumpkin production. The low gross margin showed that the total variable cost was high at ₦69, 200. High variable cost might indicate the need to change the production technique, hence the need for efficient resource allocation and least cost combination of inputs. This also implied that output per unit of input was low as a result of inefficient resource utilization. This is consistent with the finding of Ibironke

and Alakija (2018) and Osuji *et al.*, (2022) who reported the profitability of fluted pumpkin production in Southeast, Nigeria.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, it would be concluded that fluted pumpkin production in Southeast Nigeria is profitable, but the farmers were constrained by production, economic and managerial challenges.

The study recommended that:

1. Extension agents in the study area should be encouraged by providing favourable conditions of service to promote quality extension service delivery to improve the effectiveness of fluted pumpkin production in the study area.

2. Modern storage and vegetable processing facilities should be provided to reduce deterioration and losses of the produce in the study area.

3. There is need for farmers and youths who are yet to engage in agriculture especially fluted pumpkin production to tenaciously embrace its cultivation due to its economic viability, profitability, productivity and sustainability in Southeast Nigeria.

4. Government should also assist the fluted pumpkin growers in providing the needed inputs especially improved varieties to enhance fluted pumpkin production in the zone.

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